

DC Electrical Conductivity and Band Gap Tailoring for Sn Doped TiO₂ Nanoparticles

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Abstract: Materials in nanoscale can exhibit sensational results with small variation in its state with many applications in nanoscale devices. Doping is one of the techniques to vary the band gap as well as size of the nanoparticles, attempt has been made to control the band gap and size of the nanoparticle by doping Sn to TiO₂ nanoparticles synthesized by peptization method. From XRD and SEM images it confirms the crystallinity and surface morphology. The structural parameters and the size of the particle can be controlled by appropriate amount of doping in to host lattice. The particle size varies between 40.5nm to 92nm for the doping concentration 10% to pristine respectively, EDAX peaks show there is no extra phase, UV-spectra and Tauc plot confirms the tailored band gap of the material varies from 2.99eV to 3.09eV. These samples were subjected to DC Electrical conductivity studies from RT to 400°C, from Arrhenius plot clearly we encountered activation energy starts from 0.29 eV to 1.69eV for pristine to 10% doped sample respectively, decrease in the conductivity for the decrease in particle size due to hopping of charge carriers and it dominant with phonon scattering phenomenon. In partly reduced TiO₂, oxygen vacancies are formed in the oxygen ion lattice which in turn ionizes to form free electrons, due to this there is an increase in the conductivity with temperature and show the semiconductor nature of the prepared sample.

Keywords: Peptization; Crystallinity; Tauc plot; Arrhenius plot.

References:

1. K. Madhusudan Reddy et al, J. Materials Chemistry and Physics. 78 (2002) 239.